

Geochemical and isotopic (Sm-Nd) evidences for two contrasting Late Ediacaran series in SW Iberian Massif

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The Cadomian basement in central and southern Europe is composed by Late Ediacaran-Cambrian rock complexes that appear dismembered as part of different geotectonic zones along the Variscan Orogen, formed in Devonian and Carboniferous times during the main stages of the Pangea assembly. The stratigraphic record of these ancient series contains geochemical and isotopic clues about the origin and evolution of different basins along the Gondwana margin, whose current location does not correspond in some cases with their original position on the African paleo-margin. The southern branch of the Variscan Orogen, the Iberian Massif, contains an excellent stratigraphic record of Ediacaran and Paleozoic sedimentary series in addition to several sutures generated during the long convergence and collision between Gondwana and Laurussia. The nature of the boundary between an autochthonous domain (Central Iberian Zone) and the allochthonous domains (Ossa-Morena Complex) in the SW of Iberian Massif, is under discussion. Previous interpretations, based on U-Pb geochronology of detrital zircons, have suggested that the Ediacaran and Early Paleozoic sedimentary series from the Central Iberian Zone were deposited in more eastern locations along the Gondwana margin than the equivalent series of the Ossa-Morena Complex. However, whole rock geochemistry and Sm-Nd isotope sources of the contemporary siliciclastic series of the Central Iberian Zone and the Ossa-Morena Complex have not yet been compared, bearing in mind they allow a reliable time-resolved comparison between different crustal sectors. The present research compares the whole rock geochemical data and Sm-Nd isotopic tracers of two analogous Ediacaran siliciclastic series (c. 565 Ma), located on both sides of the Central Iberian Zone – Ossa-Morena Complex boundary. The comparison is established for very close domains of both regions: the southernmost sector of Central Iberian Zone, including only the Lower Unit of the so-called Schist and Greywacke Complex (Lower Alcudian), and the Serie Negra Unit (Black Series) of the northernmost part of the Ossa-Morena Complex, designated as the Obejo-Valsequillo Domain.

The Serie Negra Unit has traditionally been divided into two formations, from bottom to top: the Montemolín Formation, whose maximum depositional age has been estimated at c. 590 Ma, and the Tentudía Formation (c. 565-541 Ma). With the exception of the Mérida Massif, the exposed section of the Serie Negra within the Obejo-Valsequillo Domain belongs to the upper part of the Tentudía Formation, and is composed by metasandstones, volcanogenic metagreywackes, slates and phyllites, black quartzites, metacherts and layers of micaschists and limestones. Major and trace geochemical data of the Serie Negra and Lower Alcudian siliciclastic rocks (mainly metagreywackes) are consistent with an immature character of the samples and a limited alteration in the source area. All the study samples follow similar Post Archean Australian Shale and Upper Continental Crustal patterns, suggesting an igneous provenance. Likewise, their geochemical features suggest an active margin setting as the most probable context for the deposition of both Ediacaran sedimentary series. Nevertheless, the Sm-Nd composition of the Serie Negra shows a range of higher negative $\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(0)}$ and $\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(565)}$ values (-9.8 to -20.5 and -4.0 to -13.9, respectively), relative to the Lower Alcudian values (-6.4 to -8.8 and -1.4 to -3.0, respectively). TDM model ages of the Serie Negra range from Mesoproterozoic to Paleoproterozoic (1421-2040 Ma) and are significantly older than those of the Lower

Alcudian series (1256-1334 Ma). These isotopic results would situate the source areas of the Serie Negra in the periphery of a cratonic region, likely in the realm of the West African Craton. This old cratonic isotope sources would be mixed with other younger sources, probably derived from the nearby Ediacaran magmatic arc. However, the different Nd model ages of the Lower Alcudian indicate source areas isotopically younger than those for the Serie Negra, which would suggest deposition at distant eastern sections along the Gondwana margin.

According to these data, the contrasting Sm-Nd isotopic sources make it hard to sustain that the siliciclastic rocks of the Lower Alcudian and Serie Negra were deposited close to one another. The current boundary between the Central Iberian Zone and Ossa-Morena Complex (Obejo-Valsequillo Domain) may represent a zone with significant tectonic transport. A major Variscan thrusting developed in a dextral convergence setting can achieve the juxtaposition of distant terranes, as required for the Ediacaran series along this boundary. A similar approach could be likely investigated in other areas with similar geology along the Variscan Orogen, where there are available data to test the existence of major tectonic boundaries in the absence of clear structural and petrological indicators.

Keywords: Sm-Nd isotopic geochemistry; Ediacaran series; Central Iberia-Ossa Morena boundary; Iberian Massif.